

An Augmented String Instrument Architecture Created With Pure Data

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ABSTRACT

The Pure Data (Pd) visual programming language is a powerful tool not only for digital signal processing but also as a platform for developing robust synthesis workstations. This paper examines the architectural implementation of Pd in a new digital/acoustic augmented stringed instrument, the EV. Conceived as a feature-rich synthesis platform, Pd is used to build a modular, real-time environment that integrates external hardware sensors, feature extraction, synthesis modules, a flexible mixer for routing audio between modules, a control matrix, preset management, and an ambisonic encoder/decoder. Emphasizing system organization and architectural design, this framework demonstrates how Pd can support a synthesis environment that is both extensible and adaptable to the evolving requirements of an augmented string instrument.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pure Data (Pd) is widely recognized for its flexible and powerful digital signal processing capabilities; it can also function as a compelling platform for building full-featured synthesis workstations. Over the past five years, Pd has been used in the development of a new hybrid digital-acoustic stringed instrument, the EV (Figure 1). Beyond serving as a digital signal processing (DSP) engine, Pd was used to build a framework that integrates a network of modules that handle external sensor communication, feature extraction, synthesis, audio and control routing, preset management, and multichannel spatialization. This paper details the instrument’s design considerations and the use of Pd in developing a feature-rich, extensible, and performance-oriented system architecture.

2. EV OVERVIEW

The EV is an augmented string instrument designed to explore the boundaries between digital and acoustic sound. While interfaces using buttons and knobs have commonly been used in the creation of digital music, bowed string options have been more rare, despite their idiomatic possibilities. Played like a 16” viola, the 3D-printed EV employs FFT algorithms to convolve acoustic input from the

instrument’s four strings with synthesized sound that follows each string’s envelope and pitch. The resulting sound exhibits both the dynamic nuance of a bowed string instrument and the rich possibilities of a synthesizer.

Conceived as a full-featured synthesis platform, the EV’s Pd-based framework supports new processing modules in addition to a suite of existing ones. Current processing modules include three synthesizers, four FFT convolution algorithms, a physical model, reverb, grain delay, and a buffer freeze effect for each of the 11 mixer channels. Taking advantage of Pd’s multichannel capabilities, signal paths support up to eight channels (the ambisonic encoder supports 16), allowing modules to both synthesize and process multiple voices. Between its synthesizers and effects processors, the instrument is currently able to produce a theoretical 324 simultaneous voices.

A matrix allows control sources to modulate a wide range of parameters across the system, integrating classic synthesizer functionality into a bowed instrument paradigm. Currently, six modulation sources and 16 destinations are implemented. Each string is individually instantiated, allowing the aforementioned capabilities to be configured on a per-string basis.

From the outset, the EV was designed for both live performance and studio-composed music. As such, the EV features reasonable latency (as low as 27-39 ms, depending on the DSP used) [1], a preset management system, and a flexible spatialization system adaptable to a variety of speaker arrays. To date, the EV has been used to compose two albums [2][3] and has been featured in live performances [4][5]. Extending its synthesis capabilities to other instruments, the EV software can accept and process external signals, inheriting a capacity common to classic synthesizers such as the Korg MS-20. In this format it was used to compose *experiments from the n-space* [6]. Compositionally, the FFT convolution has proven convincing, producing results that inherit qualities from both the instrument’s acoustic strings and its synthesis engines [1].

A central concern throughout its development has been the creation of a system architecture that is reliable, extensible, and aligned with the creative evolution of the instrument. Both the macro-level functionality of the overall EV framework and the micro-level functionality of individual systems (e.g., preset management) have been carefully considered.

The EV’s implementation is part of a lineage of other Pd-based hardware and software digital instruments, as well as solution-specific systems, such as preset management

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Figure 1. EV 2.5 with its processing box (housing a quad preamp and Bela) and IR pickup hood.

implementations.

3. RELATED PD INSTRUMENTS AND ECOSYSTEMS

Pd-based instruments vary greatly in their architecture. In some cases, the system may be fixed: the configurability of the system lies in the user interface (UI) created with Pd. In others, the system is unfixed: its configurability lies both in the UI and in the Pd code itself, which can be considered part of the interface. As a further consideration, some systems are designed to be extensible, providing a programmer's interface whereby the additional functionality can be added. These architectures reflect varying design needs and priorities and form an important context for understanding the EV's software framework, which in some instances mirrors these approaches and in others diverges from them.

3.1 Instruments

The SynthBerry Pi [7], by Costantino and Fabrizio Rizzuti, consists of a Raspberry Pi running Pd housed in a chassis with eight faders. Six faders control the frequency and amplitude of three synthesizers, while the remaining two control the delay time and feedback. Each synth abstraction is defined with arguments that connect it to an internal OSC (Open Sound Control) communication network and to the audio output. The SynthBerry Pi has been used for several performances and studio recordings.

Based on the PDSynth modular toolkit, the system is easily extensible and reprogrammable; other implementations include filters, envelope generators, and different types of oscillators. The architecture serves the design's needs while remaining open-ended, offering a flexible and extensible foundation for further development.

The SynthBerry Pi implementation closely parallels that

of the EV: its internal framework is fixed, but its interface offers a range of control that supports diverse creative contexts. Additionally, the modular framework facilitates future expansion or modification. By contrast, other instruments, such as Smomid, favor piece-specific patching logic.

Smomid (String Modeling MIDI Device) by Nick Demopoulos [8] is a guitar-like controller used in conjunction with Pyramidi, a box-shaped controller. Featuring joysticks, FSRs, potentiometers, and buttons, the instrument interfaces with a laptop running Pd [8]. Like the SynthBerry Pi, Smomid omits a GUI, instead employing onboard controls, lights, and displays for visual feedback. Implementing multiple sequencers, synthesizers, and effects, a global system clock keeps the various modules in sync. The signal processing structure can vary: in some pieces, the bass sequencer drives the pitch of drum sounds; in others, it takes its cues from a synthesizer arpeggiator, aligning its output to reflect the harmonic structure in real time. While Smomid emphasizes piece-specific programming, other instruments, like Automatonism, are built with reprogrammability and live reconfiguration at their core.

Reminiscent of a modular synthesis environment, Automatonism (Johan Eriksson) [9] provides a workspace with a plethora of oscillators, sequencers, modulators, and other types of processors. Rather than abstracting user control solely to GUI objects, the system makes use of Pd's patch-cord paradigm to connect modules. Unlike systems that are fixed from piece to piece (SynthBerry Pi) or within a given piece (Smomid), Automatonism adopts an unfixed approach that expects the user to reconfigure signal flow at any time.

3.2 Preset Systems

Pd does not include a native system for saving and recalling presets. To fulfill this function, several solutions were

Figure 2. EV's flowchart

developed from within the Pd community. Kollabs/DS by Marian Weger [10] features complex scene playback and interpolation options. Built for Pd vanilla, it interfaces with the dataflow between GUI and DSP objects. In contrast, RSVP by JRS Valdez [11], was designed to avoid inserting a management object within existing code; instead `GUI-creator` dynamically creates GUI objects wrapped in abstractions that handle preset management. The EV's own preset system shares a conceptual affinity with Kollabs/DS but prioritizes a dynamic GUI interface over features like scene interpolation (see section 6.2).

4. EV IMPLEMENTATION

The design of the EV's software is reflective of the instrument's evolving requirements. Although these requirements developed in tandem with the instrument's expanding scope, they will be presented here concurrently. The software architecture is primarily shaped by the instrument's digital signal flow (Figure 2) and classic synthesizer design paradigms.

4.1 Overview

After being digitized by a Bela single board computer and transmitted to Pd running on a laptop, the pitch and envelope are derived from the four incoming signals and made available via `send~` objects to sound generation modules. The modules' output is sent to a mixer, which routes the signals via a send bus to effects such as reverb, FFT convolution, and others. Per-channel panning happens via a third-order ambisonic encoder, followed by decoding, limiting, and audio output. A matrix connects control sources to destinations, while a preset management system saves and recalls scenes. Another module handles ambisonic file playback during performance and a file writer exports the instrument's ambisonic output to disk. Lastly, since strings can be individually configured, the GUI is able to switch its display between each string's parameters (Figure 4). A focus on reliability for performance steered the system design, aiming for both reasonable CPU overhead and latency, and the use of only Pd vanilla objects.

5. STRUCTURAL DETAILS

5.1 Bela: Transmission Protocol

First, each string's signal is read by a discrete infrared pickup. In order to transmit the four pickup signals to Pd, the Bela's C++ program reads incoming analog data via its 16-bit ADC, converts the floating-point values to 16-bit integers, and writes them to an interleaved circular buffer. Data is sent to the laptop one block at a time via OSC, between successive calls to `render()`. On the laptop, Pd receives the OSC data and parses it. To reconstruct the original value (transmitted as two 8-bit bytes), the second byte (the high byte) is multiplied by 256 and added to the first byte (the low byte), effectively combining the two into a single 16-bit integer. The data is then deinterleaved: through a sorting process, each sample is identified and written to a corresponding circular buffer. A phasor object reads each buffer with a 3–5 ms delay to accommodate transmission jitter. This system¹ can accommodate a variety of block sizes and sample rates, which are negotiated during the OSC handshake.

The EV's framework consists of three main abstractions: the core, the string engine, and the GUI (Figure 2).

5.2 Pd: The Core

The core performs six primary functions: managing the program's startup sequence, hosting the aforementioned Bela protocol, loading global settings, routing messages between the three abstractions, playing audio files, and decoding ambisonic audio.

The startup sequence includes six main events: launching four instances of the string engines, connecting to the GUI (if running; the system can also operate headlessly), loading global settings, loading a preset, enabling the DSP engine, and finally raising the main output fader. This sequence ensures that all functions are initialized properly and the system loads without audible artifacts.

To maximize processing efficiency, each string engine runs on a dedicated CPU core using the `pd~` object. Al-

¹ <https://github.com/brianlindgren/Bela-to-PD-over-OSC>

Figure 3. EV's string engine, including FM synth 2 module detail. 1) DSP object, 2) Helper functions, 3) Waveshaper.

though this introduces approximately 2.9 ms of latency, the performance benefits are worth the tradeoff. The GUI is decoupled from the audio processes and runs on a separate core, launched via a shell script rather than through `pd~`. It communicates with the core using `netsend` and `netreceive`, minimizing the risk of audio dropouts caused by graphics processing under heavy load.

Configuration files provide quick access to global system settings. These include ramp times (to prevent clicks when starting or stopping audio streams), GUI update rate, ambisonic channel configuration, and preset interpolation, among others.

At times, thousands of messages per second may be sent and received across the system. Most of these relate to GUI activity, including VU meter values, matrix-controlled parameters, and per-string parameter updates (each string manages approximately 400 parameters). A routing function facilitates the transmission of messages between the GUI, core, and the four string engines.

Each message begins with an integer that indicates its destination (the GUI, a specific string, the core, or a combination thereof), followed by a parameter identifier (e.g., a synthesizer setting), and any values to be received at the destination (e.g. `4 fm2SynthOn 1`). To prevent congestion, a GUI update rate limiter is used to throttle message flow when needed.

The file player supports ambisonic audio files for use in performance. Each of the five playback engines can be assigned to a preset, allowing specific files to be triggered automatically when the corresponding preset is loaded.

The ambisonic decoder receives up to 16 channels (third-order) of audio from each string. Using a set of decoding coefficients—precomputed by a corresponding Python script—the ambisonic signal is rendered for a selectable speaker array configuration. The output is then passed through a brickwall limiter to prevent clipping at the DAC.

5.3 Pd: The String Engine

A dedicated string abstraction is instantiated for each of the EV's four strings. Its functionality can be understood in six parts: input processing, feature extraction (pitch tracking

and envelope following), sound processing modules (synthesizers and effects) (Figure 3), mixing, ambisonic encoding, matrix control, and preset management.

Input processing begins with an optional gate, compressor, and waveshaping, and then envelope following and pitch detection. Two pitch detection algorithms are available: a simple zero-crossing method² optimized for the EV, and `sigmund~`, which is suitable for a range of external instruments.

Each sound processing module includes three core components: a DSP engine (Figure 3, section 1), a set of helper functions (section 2), and a second stage of waveshaping (section 3, for synthesizers). While the DSP implementations are outside the scope of this paper, they include three synthesis engines (two FM variants and one phase distortion [1]), four convolution algorithms [12][13], and several effects (including `rev1~`, a grain delay, and a Karplus-Strong-inspired physical model).

The helper functions primarily manage whether the DSP is active, based on several conditions: the on/off state of both the string and module, the corresponding mixer channel and send level (no processing needed if muted), and the presence of lingering output signal (e.g., a decaying reverb tail). An additional helper, `dspSavr`, is used to prevent CPU spikes when multiple modules are turned on simultaneously—typically during preset changes—by enabling only one module per DSP cycle. `dspLmanager` (DSP Lock Manager), allows the user to manually lock modules in the on state, overriding automatic conditions. This helps reduce the possibility of audio dropouts during performance by maintaining a more consistent system state.

The output of each module connects to a corresponding mixer channel, which consists of four stages: an optional buffer freeze effect (based on a Pd PaulStretch implementation [14]), output leveling (via fader and mute), optional routing via the send bus, and ambisonic panning and encoding. Each mixer channel supports up to eight voices, allowing, for example, an eight-voice synthesizer to route each voice to a corresponding reverb instance, which may

² <https://github.com/brianlindgren/zDet>

then be discretely panned within the ambisonic dome.

As with the sound processing modules, each mixer channel includes helper functions that ensure DSP is active only when needed, reducing CPU load.

Finally, the audio signal is routed to an ambisonic panner/encoder, with a corresponding X/Y joystick and elevation slider in the GUI. The joystick sets both the azimuth position and the spread of individual voices: near the center, the spread is wide; near the edges, it narrows (see section 6.3). These positions, along with elevation, are encoded into an ambisonic signal and sent to the core for decoding and output.

The EV system includes a matrix for routing modulation sources to destination parameters. Sources include the amplitude envelope, spectral centroid, two LFOs, a custom-drawn envelope, and a gate triggered by the playing of pre-selected notes.

The matrix is designed to be scalable. Each destination is implemented using a specific abstraction, which contains a nested *sources* abstraction for each possible modulation source. Inside each source abstraction, three key functions are performed: communication with the GUI, scaling of the source signal, and tracking of the destination's active state. This last function enables GUI elements (e.g. sliders) to be automated, reflecting control of the source signal.

The preset management system is local to each string, the core, and the GUI. With approximately 400 parameters per string, this architecture avoids the need to route large amounts of data across the system during preset changes. The preset engine performs four main functions: staying in sync with the GUI, loading banks of presets, loading individual presets, and saving presets.

Because reading from disk can cause audio dropouts, the system loads an entire bank of presets into memory ahead of time. A 'setList' text file defines the order of the presets within the bank. Presets are loaded from their corresponding text files into dynamically created `text define` objects, with one object instantiated for each individual preset. From here, individual parameters are sent to their destinations. Saving a preset writes data both to memory and to disk.

5.4 Pd: The GUI

The GUI contains objects for all parameters the user may wish to modify (Figure 4). It includes a string selector that allows the user to choose which string's parameters are displayed, similar to a digital mixing console where a single fader strip may control multiple channels depending on the bank selection (see section 6.2).

Because each string is both an independent engine and a copy of a shared architecture, the string selector provides a way to maximize screen space while ensuring every parameter has a corresponding GUI object. In addition to the dynamically visible parameter controls, the GUI also includes static controls that are always visible. These correspond to global functions: preset management, ambisonic settings, file playback and recording, and input processing.

6. SPECIFIC DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

While much of the system's implementation was straightforward, some components required creative problem-

solving.

6.1 Extensibility

Designed as a platform for exploring synthesis possibilities with a string instrument, the EV system prioritizes extensibility.

6.1.1 Sound modules

Once a new sound module and its corresponding GUI element have been developed, they can be integrated into the system through a defined procedure.

First, a unique string identifier is assigned to the new module. This identifier allows the module to integrate with both the system architecture and its corresponding mixer channel. It is used as the first argument for all the module's new objects. Second, an abstraction is created to house the module along with its CPU-saving helper functions. Then, a corresponding mixer channel is instantiated within both the string and GUI. Finally, uniquely named preset objects are assigned to each of the module's parameters, both in the GUI and in the string engine.

6.1.2 Matrix sources & destinations

As the EV's modulation matrix expanded, the original fixed-order design became too rigid to scale. Initially, only a few sources and destinations were supported, and their integration relied on strict numerical order. To make the system more flexible, each source and destination is now assigned a unique identifier. When a new destination is created in the string engine, it instantiates corresponding matrix source objects to receive and route control signals. Likewise, when a new modulation source is added, an abstraction is placed into each destination, dynamically updating the full matrix.

In the GUI, adding a new source abstraction creates a row of objects with a source amount slider on the left and destination toggles on the right. The row uses the source ID as its argument to link it to the system. When a new destination abstraction is added, a small canvas with a toggle and corresponding preset object is instantiated and added to the row of toggles, and initialized with the source and destination IDs.

6.2 GUI Screen Switcher

While the instrument was always polyphonic, early versions shared parameters across all strings. Once each string was given independent control, the GUI needed to handle four sets of parameters. To solve this, a page-based system was introduced: GUI objects display only the selected string's parameters. When the string number (1-4) is selected in the string switcher (Figure 4, section 19), the GUI will update to reflect the selected string. Selecting "A" (for all strings) copies the current string's settings to the other strings. Subsequent updates apply to all strings.

This functionality was added directly into the preset object for each parameter, which contains four sub-objects (one per string). Each sub-object handles GUI updates, saves its value to the preset system, and, if matrix control is active, allows control sources to modulate the parameter. An issue arose when applying this functionality to the waveshaper display: switching between full-resolution

Figure 4. EV’s GUI. 1) Input processing. 2) Waveshaper tables. Modules: 3) Synthesizers. 4) FFT convolution engines, with settings for sample rate, overlap, window size, input swap, and source selection. 5) FFT window type 6) Karplus-Strong effect. 7) Granular delay. 8) Reverb. 9) Mixer. 10) Buffer freeze, with settings for overlap, window size, playback rate, and refresh. 11) CV matrix. Modulation sources: 12) Spectral centroid. 13) LFOs. 14) Envelope generator. 15) Note trigger. 16) Ambisonics options. 17) File playback. 18) Output recording. 19) String switcher: current string displayed. 20) DSP lock (on) manager. 21) Settings reload. 22) System stats/troubleshooting. 23) Tuner. 24) Panning joystick.

24-bit tables caused CPU strain. To fix this, a dual-table system was implemented. The GUI displays a lightweight 512-point “thumbnail” version, while the engine uses the full-resolution table. If a user draws a custom curve, a new 24-bit table is generated and saved automatically.

6.3 Joystick Panning

With the upgrade from monophonic to ambisonic output, a challenge emerged: implementing a two-axis GUI panning control not available in Pd vanilla. The solution uses two nested canvases: the smaller knob-like canvas as the joystick, and the larger as a bounding box (Figure 4, section 24).

On `loadbang`, the bounding box position is retrieved using `get_pos`. The joystick is polled at the GUI update rate, and its X/Y offset relative to the box is used to calculate azimuth. Joystick position can also be set programmatically using `pos $1 $2` when loading presets or displaying control modulation. This has been used for automated panning, including spatial modulation synthesis [15]. An implementation of this system, with the ambisonic engine, has been released³.

6.4 VoiceTrack

With each sound generator supporting up to eight voices, the EV’s routing system manages voice activation. To avoid unnecessary CPU load, effect processors need to activate only as many voices as required by the generators sending signal to them. A voice-tracking system handles this: when a send bus routes to a receiving effect (e.g., FM1 to reverb), it also transmits its voice count to a `voiceTrack` abstraction, which stores the voice counts of all connected modules. The system reports the highest count, which determines the active voice count for the effect, ensuring full polyphonic coverage with minimal CPU overhead.

³ <https://github.com/brianlindgren/ambiNilla>

7. FUTURE WORK

While the EV system architecture has come a long way, further updates are underway. Notably, the system is at a pivotal juncture: its Pd-based design is being reimplemented in C++ to run efficiently on an embedded Bela Mini rather than a laptop. This recoding process, ongoing over the past year, has also influenced the structure of the original Pd code, encouraging a gradual shift toward greater modularity. Though the Pd version has improved significantly as a result, additional refinements are still in progress.

One such update involves creating an alternate signal path between sound generators and the mixer to support spatially informed synthesis, in which spatial location is assigned during synthesis rather than at the output stage. While the current system applies spatialization at the mixer, techniques such as spatial granular synthesis would benefit from assigning position to each grain at the point of generation.

This would allow the mixer to focus on global transformations—such as field rotation or scaling—while a parallel signal routing system operates alongside the existing one to support both approaches.

In addition, the creation of a simplified GUI or overlay for the EV is planned. Instead of exposing hundreds of parameters, this interface will present a small set of macro controls, each adjusting multiple parameters behind the scenes.

Inspired by analog modular design, this layer will offer a more performance-friendly interface while retaining the system’s depth. Macros will reflect distinct sonic signatures and support intuitive control in both live and studio contexts.

8. CONCLUSION

This paper has described the Pd-based software framework developed for the EV, an augmented string instrument. De-

signed to be both extensible and capable of supporting complex synthesis strategies, the system architecture has evolved significantly through continued use, testing, and redesign. Built with modularity as a central principle, the framework distributes its processing across six CPU cores to maximize computational power and maintain responsiveness in real-time performance contexts.

Throughout the development process, various design challenges have been encountered—from GUI synchronization and preset management to dynamic signal routing and voice allocation—and addressed through purpose-built solutions. While numerous updates and refinements remain planned, the instrument has already reached a mature and musically effective state. The EV is now used regularly in both live performance and the composition of studio-based albums, demonstrating the system’s reliability, flexibility, and expressive potential.

Acknowledgments

Thank you to my mentors, teachers, and friends from the Brooklyn College Sonic Arts program and the University of Virginia’s Composition and Computer Technologies program, whose support has been invaluable in realizing the EV.

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